

**New subspecies of *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszehi* Kraatz, 1873
from Georgia, Armenia and Turkey
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Taxonomy, zoogeography, new subspecies, new synonyms, Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion)*, Armenia, Georgia, Turkey.

Abstract: The nominative subspecies is redescribed with type locality adjusted. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszehi cavernosum*, **ssp. n.** is described from Armenia and Turkey. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszehi georgianum ssp. n.* is described from Georgia. New synonyms are proposed: *Dorcadion semibrunneum mediocreimpressum* Pic, 1909 = *Dorcadion semibrunneum anamasum* Pic, 1934, **syn. nov.** The taxon is retained as a subspecies.

Several abbreviations are used in the text:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow

ML - collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow

ZMM - Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow

SDEI - Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszehi* Kraatz, 1873**

(Figs 1-11)

Dorcadion mniszehii Kraatz, 1873: 39 - „Caucasus“;

Dorcadion (s. str.) *mniszehii*, Ganglbauer, 1884: 480 - “Grusien”.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszehi, Pic, 1901: 12 (incorrect subsequent spelling in prevailing usage - Art. 33.3.1. - ICZN, 1999); Aurivillius, 1922: 26 - “Kaukasus”; Winkler 1929: 1187 - Caucasus; Plavilstshikov, 1932: 192 - South Transcaucasia; 1948: 126 - Sevan, Daralagez; (West Azerbaijan, North Iran, West Armenia, Asia Minor); Breuning, 1943: 524, fig 4; 1948: 512 - “l’Asie mineure”; 1958: 35, part. (including ssp. *anamasum* Pic and ssp. *semibrunneum* Pic); 1962: 527, part. (including ssp. *anamasum* Pic, ssp. *semibrunneum* Pic and m. *shirvanicum* Bog.) - “Armenien: Khashkash Dagh., Mt. Alagoes, Kasikoporan”; Danilevsky et al., 2005: 137 (endophallus), 148; Özdikmen, 2007: 303, 365, 391, part. (including ssp. *semibrunneum* Pic); Danilevsky, 2010: 250 - Armenia, Georgia, Turkey.

Dorcadion mniszehi mniszehi, Bogatchev, 1934: 70.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) mniszehi, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 126 (including North

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Iran); 1958: 104, part. (including *shirvanicum* Bog.); Lobanov et al., 1982: 263 - Caucasus, Near East, South-West Asia; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 328, part. (including “*Dorcadion mniszzechi shirvanicum* Bogatschew”) - Armenia (Talin, Nairi, Aparan, Sevan Lake), East Georgia, East Azerbaijan; Turkey.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) mniszzechi mniszzechi, Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 17.

Dorcadion mniszzechi, Danilevsky, 1986: 68 (species needs to be protected).

Type locality. The species is represented in Transcaucasia and Turkey by several very different populations, which must be described as several subspecies, so the exact definition of the type locality is necessary. The species was described from “Caucasus” without any specification. It was impossible to find the type in German museums. Several very old specimens (Fig. 1) collected near Kazkoporan (Iğdir) in Turkey, 40°1'7"N, 43°26'12"E [“Kasikoporan”, which was included that time in Caucasus] are preserved now in European museums. Besides the populations of Central Armenia from Mt. Arailer to Sevan Lake are very similar to Iğdir specimens. I preliminary accept here that form as typical. So, the type locality occupies the Transcaucasian area from Iğdir prov. in Turkey to Sevan Lake in Armenia.

Diagnosis. Body totally black, as well as antennae and legs; head with fine, often hardly visible, longitudinal line, which is better pronounced on vertex; frons and vertex with fine scattered punctation, frons interspaces smooth or with hardly visible micropunctation; vertex interspaces with distinct micropunctation; if micropunctation absent, then the cuticle more or less shining; male antennae surpassing elytral middle, female antennae not reaching or hardly surpassing elytral middle; lateral tubercles of prothorax strongly developed, rounded; pronotum smooth with very fine scattered punctation, often indistinct in males and so strongly shining; abdomen with short brownish setae; elytra glabrous, without setae stripes; male elytra with rough cavernous sculpture; female elytra much smoother, sometimes quite smooth; body length in males: 16.9-26.1 mm, width: 5.8-8.1 mm; body length in females: 18.5-25.0 mm; width: 7.3-10.1 mm.

Distribution. Armenia: from the northwest border (Ashotzk) to the central areas (Arailer Mt., Khosrov, Sevan Lake, Arzakan, Arteni);

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Georgia: Gori, Grakali, Norio (10 km NE Tbilisi), Signakhi, Tsiteli Tskaro [Dedoplis Tskaro - "Krasnye Kolodtsy"], Eldar area; Turkey: Kars (Kars-city environs, Kagyzman, Khashkhash-Dagh), İğdir (Kazkoporan, Tuzluka).

The record for East Azerbaijan (Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985) was connected with wrong old attribution (Bogachev, 1934; Plavilstshikov, 1958; Breuning, 1962) of *D. shirvanicum* Bogachev, 1934 to *D. mniszeechi*. The record for Iran (Urmia Lake) by Plavilstshikov (1958) repeated by Villiers (1967: 368 - as *Cribridorcadion mniszeechi*) was unbelievable and could be connected with totally black glabrous females of local species.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszeechi mniszeechi Kraatz, 1873
(Figs 1-5)

Dorcadion mniszeechii Kraatz, 1873: 39 - „Caucasus“.

Dorcadion mniszeechi mniszeechi, Bogatchev, 1934: 70, part.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) mniszeechi mniszeechi, Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 17, part.

Type locality. Transcaucasian area from İğdir prov. in Turkey to Sevan Lake in Armenia (see above).

Diagnosis. Males with moderately rough elytral sculpture; females elytra often totally smooth; body length in males: 17.0-26.1 mm, width: 6.7-8.1 mm; body length in females: 18.5-25.0 mm; width: 7.6-9.1 mm.

Distribution. Armenia: Arailer Mountain, Arzakan environs, Sevan-city environs, Khosrov natural reserve; Turkey, İğdir: Kazkoporan [40°17'N, 43°26'12"E], Tuzluca [“Kulp”, 40°2'30"N, 43°39'46"E].

Material. 3 males, 2 females, “Armenia circ. lac. Gokcha, pr. Babadjan-dara, 15.05.1930, A. Schelk.” - ZMM; 1 female, Armenia, Arailer, 29.05.1971 - MD; 1 female, Arzakan, 05.06.1981 - MD; 6 males, 2 females, Armenia, Arailer, 07.05-09.05.1983, M.Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Arailer, 23.05.1985, M.Kalashyan - MD; 1 male, Khosrov, 30.05.1986, Eranyan - MD; 3 females, Arailer, 24.05.1987, M.Kalashyan - MD; 1 female, Arailer, 28.05.1993, M.Kalashyan - MD; 1 male, Armenia, Arailer, 02.06.1993, M.Kalashyan - MD; 5 males, 1 female, Arailer, 2000 m., 18.06.2003, M.Danilevsky - MD; 4 males, 4 females, Arailer, 1900 m, 40°24'N, 44°27'E, 21-22.06.2003, M.Danilevsky - MD, ML.

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***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszechi georgianum* ssp. n.**

(Figs 10-11)

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) mniszechi, Plavilstshikov, 1958: 104, part. (including Georgia, but only Eldar area along small mountains near Eldar Steppe).

Type locality. Georgia: Grakali environs, 670 m, 41°56'59"N, 44°17'34"E.

Diagnosis. Males with extremely rough elytra, with shallow big conjugated dots; female elytra never totally smooth, usually with small scattered punctation and fine wrinkles; several females with rather rough sculpture; lateral pronotal tubercles distinctly longer than in the nominative subspecies; body length in males: 16.9-22.5 mm, width: 5.8-7.5 mm; body length in females: 18.5-24.0 mm; width: 7.3-8.4 mm.

Distribution. Georgia: Gori env., Grakali, 670 m, 41°56'59"N, 44°17'34"E; 10 km NE Tbilisi, Norio, 1000 m, 41°48'37"N, 44°58'43"E; Signakhi environs; Tsiteli Tskaro [Dedoplis Tskaro - "Krasnye Kolodtsy", 41°27'54"N, 46°06'16"E].

Material. Holotype, male, "Gori, Grakali, 5.4.89, 600-800 m, M. Danilevsky leg." - MD; 19 paratypes: 5 males, 4 females, with same label - MD; 1 male, 1 female, "Transcauc., Eldar distr., Signach, 16.04.926" - ZMM; 1 female, "Eiljār [Eldari]" - ZMM; 2 females, "Transcaucasus, Krasnye Kolodtsy, 19.05.1929, V. Bogachev" - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Georgia, 10 km NE Tbilisi, Norio, 1000 m., 06.04.2010, local collector- MD; 2 males, Georgia, NE Tbilisi, Norio env. (about 41°46'N, 44°54'E), 850m, 18.04.2010, I. Pliushch leg. - MD; 1 male, same locality, 18.04.2010, A. Gubin leg. - A. Gubin collection (Donetsk).

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszechi cavernosum* ssp. n.**

(Figs 6-9)

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszechii, Breuning, 1946: 96, part. - „Kasipokoran (sic! - ML), Arménie“; 1962: 527, part. - “Armenien: Khashkash Dag., Mt. Alagoes, Kasikoporan”.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszechii m. *rugulosum* Breuning, 1946: 96 (unavailable name) - „Kasipokoran (sic! - ML), Arménie“.

Type locality. Armenia: Arteni environs (40°17'50"N, 43°45'47"E).

Diagnosis. Males with very rough elytral sculpture, punctures deep

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and conjugated; female elytra never smooth, always with distinct punctation and wrinkles; a big female from Kagyzman with slightly tubercular elytra; specimens from near Kars-city with strongly elevated humeral carinae accompanied by deep internal furrows; lateral thoracic tubercles relatively small; body length in males: 18.5-20.7 mm, width: 7.1-8.0 mm; body length in females: 20.1-24.8 mm; width: 7.4-10.1 mm.

Distribution. Armenia: Arteni environs (40°17'50"N, 43°45'47"E), Ashotsk environs, Tsogamarg, 2000 m, 40°56'53"N, 43°51'22"E; Turkey: Kars-city environs, Kagysman, Khashkhash-Dagh (Geröll-Südabhang).

Material. Holotype, male, "Arm. SSR, Arteni, 18.05.1983, M.Danilevsky" [in Russian] - MD; 9 paratypes: 1 male, 3 females, Arteni, 18.05.1983, M.Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Armenia, Gukasyan [now Ashotsk] env., Tsogamarg, 29.05.1986, P. Kazaryan leg. - MD; 1 male, "Transcaucasia, pr. Kagysman, 05-06.1916, E.V.B." - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, "Kars env., Strelb. [Strelbishche = shooting ground] 25.04.1915, Olsufev" - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, "Armenien, Khashkhash-Dagh, Geröll-Südabhang, 3200 m. 1.-10.7. leg. Kotzsch" - MD.

Remarks. Plavilstshikov (1958: 107) mentioned, that a subgenus *Cribridorcadion* Pic, established for *D. mniszzechi* Kr. only was totally an artificial group because the peculiarity of elytral sculpture was the character of species level and was similar to elytra of "*D. infernale* var. *rugosum*". His point of view was totally supported by endophallus characters (Danilevsky et al., 2005), and that is why *D. mniszzechi* was joined with many "*Pedestredorcadion*" in one subgenus under the oldest name *Cribridorcadion* Pic.

Plavilstshikov (1958) wrongly included *D. shirvanicum* Bogatchev, 1934 in *D. mniszzechi* on the base of a glabrous female, and so prolonged the area of the species to about Apsheron Peninsula. Later pubescent specimens of *D. shirvanicum* were described by him as *D. azerbaijdzhanicum* Plavilstshikov, 1937. The mistake was repeated by Danilevsky & Miroshnikov (1985).

Several authors (Breuning, 1962; Özdikmen, 2007) included *D. semibrunneum* Pic, 1903 (described from Eskişehir: "Anatolie: Bos-Dagh") in *D. mniszzechi* as a subspecies. In fact *D. semibrunneum* strongly differs from *D. mniszzechi* by brown color

and rounded humeral carinae and must be accepted as another species (Pic, 1909; Danilevsky, 2010).

The taxon known (Danilevsky, 2010) as *D. semibrunneum anamasum* Pic, 1934 (Pisidischer Taurus, Mts Anamas) was in fact described much before as *D. mniszehi* var. *mediocreimpresum* Pic, 1909 from same locality, as it is clear from the label of the holotype preserved in Pic's collection (Paris): "Anamas Gbg.", so *D. semibrunneum mediocreimpresum* Pic, 1909 = *D. s. anamasum* Pic, 1934, **syn. nov.** Later the name was published by Pic with wrong orthography: "*Dorcadion semibrunneum* var. *medioimpresum*, Pic, 1910" – unavailable name published as a synonym by Breuning (1962), Danilevsky (2010). The taxon was recently upgraded to species rank by Pesarini & Sabbadini (2013) as *D. anamasum* based on a male from Çakmaktepe Geçidi (Afyonkarahisar) - 38°28'25"N, 30°23'19"E (about 100 km north-westwards from Anamas Mts.). I know a male [MD] from Barla Mt. (38°3'12"N, 30°39'40"E - about 40 km from Anamas Mts.) very similar to the specimen figured by Pesarini & Sabbadini (2013). The holotypes of "var. *mediocreimpresum*" and "var. *anamasum*" are females and adequate comparison of available specimens (males) with types is impossible, so populations from Çakmaktepe Geçidi and from Barla Mt. can represent a new subspecies.

Now *D. semibrunneum* consists of three subspecies: *D. s. semibrunneum* Pic, 1903, *D. s. mediocreimpresum* Pic, 1909 and *D. s. notatum* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2013 (Bala dint., prov. Ankara) with very distinct white suture stripe. Its bibliography must look as:

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) semibrunneum* Pic, 1903**

Dorcadion mniszehi var. *semibrunneum* Pic, 1903: 170 - "Anatolie: Bos-Dagh",
[type labels: Eski-Chehir, Bos-Dagh].

Dorcadion semibrunneum, Pic, 1909: 123 (without locality).

Dorcadion mniszehi var. *mediocreimpresum* Pic, 1909: 123 (without locality)
[♀20mm, type label: "Anamas Gbg."].

Dorcadion semibrunneum var. *medioimpresum*, Pic, 1910: 5 (without locality)
[wrong posterior spelling - unavailable]

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) semibrunneum semibrunneum, Danilevsky, 2010: 263,
part. (including *mediocreimpresum* Pic and *medioimpresum* Pic, 1910 as
synonyms); Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2013: 63, part.:

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) semibrunneum anamasum, Danilevsky, 2010: 263.
part.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) semibrunneum notatum Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2013:

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62, part. - "Bala dint. (prov. Ankara)".
Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) anamasum, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2013: 63, part.

CORRECTION

An unfortunate misprint was published in my previous article (Lazarev, 2014). The new taxon was wrongly proposed as "*Cleroclytus* (s.str.) *collaris savitskyi*". Its correct name is *Cleroclytus* (s. str.) *semirufus savitskyi*.

Acknowledgements. I am very grateful to Aleksey Gusakov [Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow], Mikhail Danilevsky [A.N. Severtzov Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Moscow], Igor Pliushch (Kiev) and A. Gubin (Donetsk) for supplying me with the specimens for study, to Gérard Tavakilian [Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris] and Stephan M. Blank [Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg] for the photos of the type specimens and labels.

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Figs 1-5. - *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszzechi mniszzechi* Kraatz, 1873:
1 – male, "Russ. Armen., Kulp [now Tuzluka 40°2'30"N, 43°39'46"E], 1901, Korb [leg.]", SDEI collection, photo received from Dr. S.M. Blank;

2 - male, Arailer, 1900 m., 21.06.2003, M.Danilevsky;

3 - female, Arailer, 09.05.1983, M.Danilevsky;

4 - female, Armenia, Arailer, 29.05.1971;

5 - female, Arailer, 1900 m., 21.06.2003, M.Danilevsky.

Figs 6-9. - *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszzechi cavernosum ssp. n.*:

6 - male, holotype;

7 - female, paratype, with same label;

8 - female, Armenia, Gukasyan (Ashotsk) env., Tsogamarg, 29.05.1986, P. Kazaryan;

9 - female, "Kars env. Strelb. [Strelbishche] 25.04.1915 Olsufev".

Figs 10-11. - *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) mniszzechi georgianum ssp. n.*:

10 - male, holotype;

11 - female, paratype, with same label.

Figs 12-13. - *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) semibrunneum semibrunneum*, female [holotype of “*Dorcadion mniszehi* var. *semibrunneum* Pic, 1903”], photos by G. Tavakilian.

Figs 14-15. - *Dorcadion semibrunneum mediocreimpressum*, female [holotype of “*Dorcadion mniszehi* var. *mediocreimpressum* Pic, 1909”], photos by G. Tavakilian.

Received: 15.07.2014

Accepted: 23.10.2014